

Analysis of the shell- and supershell structures of metallic nanowires with jellium models

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Abstract.

The stability of metallic nanowires is studied analysing the shell- and supershell structures of total energy oscillations. Fully quantum-mechanical calculations are performed for Cs, Na and Al nanowires covering the whole range of valence electron densities in simple metals. Nanowires are modeled as infinite stabilized jellium cylinders and solving for their electronic structure self-consistently. The results are analysed within a semiclassical model. A comparison between the shell structures of nanowires and atomic clusters is made.

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1. Introduction

During the last three or four decades the electronic industry has been able to reduce continuously the size of electronic devices. Now we are approaching the regime, that the study of atomic size structures is not only of academic interest, but the 'state-of-the-art' techniques are capable to build structures composed of a few atoms. Despite the laws of nature are the same, physical properties of macroscopic and nanoscopic systems often show different behaviors. This is due to the increasing relevance of quantum effects when the size of the system is decreased. In the case of atomic nanowires we observe, for example, conductance quantization [1, 2], unexpected magnetic solutions [3, 4], and oscillations in the physical properties [5, 6].

Experimentally, metallic nanowires can be produced by several different ways. The simplest scheme is to put two metallic protusions in contact and then pull them from each other over atomic distances. Upon pulling a nanowire is produced, further elongated and narrowed, until it eventually breaks [7]. This method is used *e.g.* in the mechanically controllable break-junction technique (MCBJ). The MCBJ measurements give histograms of observed conductance values. The histograms have a peaky structure which is interpreted to reflect electron shell- and supershell oscillations in the wire stability as a function of the neck radius [8, 9]. Thus, at particular neck radii the nanowires are especially stable. In this sense, the conductance histograms are similar to the abundance spectra for atomic clusters [10, 11].

In this work, we study the stability of nanowires by performing density-functional calculations within the local density approximation (LDA). Our main aim is to clarify the origin of the shell- and supershell structures. We solve self-consistently for the electronic structure of infinitely-long jellium wires with cylindrical symmetry. The results are then analysed within a semiclassical approximation. The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 we present the basic features of the full quantum formalism and the semiclassical model used to study the stability. In Section 3 we discuss the electronic structure results obtained with the stabilized jellium model. Section 4 contains the summary and conclusions of our work.

2. Theory

Our quantum-mechanical calculations have been performed in the framework of the density functional theory (DFT) [12]. Most of the results have been obtained with the stabilized jellium model [13, 14], in which the nanowire is considered as an infinitely long cylinder of positive homogeneous charge density $\bar{n}$ with radius R . The density $\bar{n}$ corresponds to the average valence electron density of the simple metal in question. The two parameters completely defining the system are r_s ($\bar{n} = \frac{3}{4\pi r_s^3}$) and R . The rigid positive charge is neutralized by the electron density solved by the self-consistent Kohn-Sham scheme within the LDA for the exchange-correlation effects [15, 16]. The electron states are defined by the angular momentum quantum number m , the radial

quantum number n related to the number of nodes of the radial function, and the quantum number k_z corresponding to the longitudinal linear momentum. Due to the electron confinement in the wire cross-section, quantum numbers m and n are a set of discrete eigenvalues, whereas k_z has a continuous spectrum. The practical details of our calculation scheme have been published earlier in reference [4].

The semiclassical approach [17] is valuable in studying the stability of nanowires because the oscillating part of the physical properties can be simply and transparently calculated, and then analytical expressions allows us to verify and clarify the quantum mechanical results. In this approach an electron moves classically in the transverse cross section of the wire bouncing back at the potential wall at the surface of the wire. The oscillating contribution comes from the closed orbits (see figure 2). These orbits are defined by the labels (M, Q) , where M is the number of vertices and Q is the winding number. The length L of an orbit is the important measure because it is related to the oscillation frequency of the physical properties. The most relevant electrons are those at the Fermi level, with the associated wavelength λ_F . As the wire radius increases, an integer number n of wavelengths is completed on an orbit when $L = n\lambda_F$, *i.e.*, with frequency [18]

$$\omega_{MQ} = 2\pi\nu_{MQ} = \frac{4\pi M}{\lambda_F} \sin \frac{\pi Q}{M}. \quad (1)$$

An oscillating behavior of the energy

$$E_{osc}(R) = \sum_{Q=1}^{M/2} \sum_{M=2}^{\infty} A_{MQ} \cos(2\pi\nu_{MQ}R + \phi_{MQ}) \quad (2)$$

and other properties [19, 6] is derived then. In equation (2), A_{MQ} is the weight of each orbit, ν_{MQ} is the frequency calculated with (1) and ϕ_{MQ} is the orbit phase.

3. Results

In this section we present the results for stabilized jellium wires, with densities corresponding to Al ($r_s = 2.07 a_0$), Na ($r_s = 3.93 a_0$) and Cs ($r_s = 5.62 a_0$) metals. The stabilized jellium model provides reliable values for the surface energy and other properties which are not well described by the simple jellium model [20].

In order to study the stability of metallic nanowires we analyse the energy oscillations, because wires with low energies are the most stable ones. Within our model and approximations we are able to calculate the total energy per unit length. We need to subtract from this energy the soft or mean contribution to obtain the plain energy oscillations. We have calculated the soft energy contribution using the liquid-drop model [21]. In this model the energy is the sum of the homogeneous electron gas energy plus the energy increase due to the surface. Then we can write the oscillating part of the energy per unit length as:

$$E_{osc}/L = E_{tot}[n(r)]/L - \left(\pi R^2 \epsilon_{bulk}(\bar{n}) + 2\pi R\sigma \right). \quad (3)$$

Above, $E_{tot}[n(r)]/L$ is the self-consistent total energy per unit length of the wire, $\epsilon_{bulk}(\bar{n})$ is the homogeneous electron gas energy per unit volume and σ is the surface energy per unit area, which has been calculated in the stabilized jellium model for Al, Na and Cs [21].

The energy oscillations for Al, Na and Cs are displayed in figure 1. In this figure we can observe that each energy curve oscillates around zero, meaning that the average total energy is in a good agreement with the energy calculated with the liquid-drop model. The oscillations have approximately equally-spaced energy minima (maxima), corresponding to more (less) stable wires at these radii. This structure is known as the shell structure. Nevertheless, these oscillations exhibit some beats in which the structure is not very clear (shadowed stripes in figure 1). This is the so-called supershell structure. The beats of Al wires are clearly shifted to larger radii, with respect to those of Na and Cs wires. The arrows pointing downward indicate the most stable radii found in MCBJ measurements for Na nanowires and the vertical dashed lines mark the experimental beat positions [8]. The analysis of this good agreement has been performed in our previous work [22].

The energy oscillations for the different metals can be analysed by calculating the Fourier transforms. Figure 2 shows that they are rather similar. The main peaks are centered at the same positions corresponding to given semiclassical orbits. The agreement between the peak frequencies and the frequencies calculated with equation (1) is very good. The high-frequency peaks, especially that of the five-point star orbit, are clearer for Al than for Na and Cs. This may reflect the softness of the Al potential in comparison with the Na and Cs potentials [23].

The origin of the energy oscillations is easily explained in the framework of the semiclassical theory [8, 24] as the interference between two semiclassical orbits with similar frequencies. As seen from figure 2, the two main orbits are the pendulum and triangular orbits. It is known that the interference of two oscillating functions with similar frequencies produces a modulated oscillating pattern, *i.e.*, oscillations with equally-spaced beats. Then, using (2), we can write the energy oscillations as

$$\begin{aligned} E_{osc}(R) &\sim \cos(2\pi\nu_t R + \phi_t) + \cos(2\pi\nu_p R + \phi_p) \\ &= 2 \cos\left(\pi(\nu_t + \nu_p)R + \frac{\phi_t + \phi_p}{2}\right) \cos\left(\pi(\nu_t - \nu_p)R + \frac{\phi_t - \phi_p}{2}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Above, ν_p and ν_t are the frequencies of the pendulum and triangular orbits, respectively, and ϕ_p and ϕ_t are the corresponding phases. With this formula the basic features of the energy oscillations are reproduced. The position of the k -th beat lies in the k -th zero of the second cosine at

$$R(k) = \frac{k - 1/2}{(\nu_t - \nu_p)} - \frac{\phi_t - \phi_p}{2\pi(\nu_t - \nu_p)}. \quad (5)$$

The shift in the supershell structure with decreasing r_s is clear in figure 1. It has been observed also in the case of atomic clusters [11, 10, 25, 26]. The shift is due to the softening of the potential at the surface and the ensuing rounding of the classical

orbit vertices [24, 25, 27]. The softness of the potential at the surface does not affect the orbit frequencies. This is evident from figure 2, showing that the peak positions do not change between different metals corresponding to potentials with different softness. Nevertheless, the potential softness affects the phases of the orbits. The influence is different for each orbit. This changes the interference pattern and produces the shifts in the beat positions. In our calculations the potentials for Cs and Na are quite similar and the shift in the supershell structure is too small to be observed. In contrast, the effective potential for Al is much softer than for the others, and the beat positions are clearly shifted with respect to Na and Cs.

The aim to understand the electronic structures and their effects on the physical properties of nanowires in mind, we have sketched in figure 3 the radii at which each subband begins to fill in Na and Al nanowires. The horizontal axis gives the radii at which the bottoms of different (n, m) subbands (filled squares) cross the Fermi energy. The m quantum number varies along the y-axis, and the points on each ascending diagonal have the same n quantum number. The continuous curves connect the most important quantum states belonging to the same pendulum orbit. The n quantum numbers of these states differ by 1 and the m quantum numbers by 2. The dashed curves connect the states of triangular orbits differing by 1 and 3 in their n and m quantum numbers, respectively. These two classical orbits are the most important ones, so that we have not drawn the rest for clarity. Vertical lines are placed at the radii of clear energy maxima in figure 1. The figure shows the link between the semiclassical approach and full quantum calculations. The quantum states corresponding to pendulum orbits become approximately degenerate in energy at the $m = 0$ edge. This means that the pendulum orbit closes at these positions. The triangular orbits close approximately in the region between $n = 1$ and $n = 3$ diagonals. The orbits close with frequencies given by (1). The connection between the orbit closing described above and the physical properties comes through the fact that the orbit closings take place in coincidence with introduction of new subbands below the Fermi level. New subbands will increase the density of states at the Fermi level and the total energy.

The interference between the pendulum and triangular orbits can be seen clearly in figure 3. The vertical straight lines indicate the positions of the energy maxima, and they coincide with the radii at which the pendulum and triangular orbits close at the same time. Here the interference of the two orbits is constructive producing clear energy oscillations, while in the beat regions the interference is destructive and the oscillations are fuzzy. In figure 3 it can be observed how a small variation in this spectrum from Na to Al produces the shift of the beats.

For a given metal, the shape of the potential at the wire surface depends weakly on the wire radius. This enables an easy way to reproduce the shifts in the supershell structures. We start with Na as a reference metal. Its supershell structure in energy is given by equations (4) and (5) as a function of the radius R . Then, for Al we suppose that each orbit feels a larger effective radius of $R_{eff}(M, Q) = R + \Delta R_{(M, Q)}$ due to the softer potential. This approximation introduces in equation (2) an extra phase

$\Delta\phi_{(M,Q)} = 2\pi\nu_{(M,Q)}\Delta R_{(M,Q)}$ for each orbit. By calculating the beat positions with the new phases in (5), we obtain the Al beat positions at $R'(k)$ given by

$$R'(k) = R(k) + \frac{\nu_p}{(\nu_t - \nu_p)}\Delta R_p - \frac{\nu_t}{(\nu_t - \nu_p)}\Delta R_t. \quad (6)$$

Comparing the orbit closings given in figure 3 for Na, as a function of the scaled radius R/λ_F with a similar figure for Al, we can estimate the $\Delta R_{(M,Q)}$ values. The Na and Al subbands with a given high angular momentum cross the Fermi level approximately at the same radius, *i.e.*, $\Delta R_{(3,1)} \approx 0$. Therefore, the shift is produced by the pendulum contribution. The pendulum orbits close at $m = 0$ and each $m = 0$ subband of the Al wire starts to fill before the corresponding Na subband. This means that the effective radius is larger for Al than for Na. The radius increment between the bottoms of the corresponding Na and Al $m = 0$ subbands gives $\Delta R_{(2,1)} \approx 0.033\lambda_F$. Introducing this value in (6), a shift of $\Delta R(k) \approx 0.1\lambda_F$ is obtained. This is in a very good agreement with the shift seen in figure 1 between the Al and Na energy beats. In conclusion, the small difference between the low angular momentum states of Al and Na wires produces a large difference between the interference patterns.

When the bottom of a subband crosses the Fermi level, *i.e.*, $\epsilon_{mn} = \epsilon_F$, the Fermi level density of states $\text{DOS}(\epsilon_F)$ is high, exhibiting the $\sim (\epsilon_{mn} - \epsilon_F)^{1/2}$ behavior. When the pendulum and triangular orbits close at the same time, there are many degenerate levels at the Fermi level (see figure 3) and the $\text{DOS}(\epsilon_F)$ is especially high increasing the total energy and making the wire unstable. Between two adjacent $\text{DOS}(\epsilon_F)$ maxima the number of new subbands is quite low, $\text{DOS}(\epsilon_F)$ is low so that the energy minima are placed at these radii (more stable wires). During the beats, the pendulum and triangular orbits close alternatively and $\text{DOS}(\epsilon_F)$ has an intermediate value making the wire neither specially stable nor unstable. Although quite rare, this notion can be also found in the literature. Using the semiclassical theory for infinitely long wires modelled with an infinite hard-wall potential Kassubek *et al.* [28] showed that wires deform in length at radii of high $\text{DOS}(\epsilon_F)$ values, in order to become more stable. Using more sophisticated *ab initio* calculation methods, the stability of monoatomic gold chains has been studied [29]. In the case of a linear gold atom chain the *d*-band crosses the Fermi level enhancing $\text{DOS}(\epsilon_F)$ and destabilized the wire. When the gold atoms are arranged in to a zigzag geometry, the *d* states are pushed down below the Fermi level. This lowers the $\text{DOS}(\epsilon_F)$ making the zigzag configuration to the most stable one.

The supershell structures of atomic clusters have been widely studied, both theoretically and experimentally [11, 10]. In clusters, the energy oscillations result from the interference between the triangular and square orbits. The pendulum orbit is not important due to a low degeneracy factor. The frequencies of the triangular and square orbits are closer to each others than those for pendulum and triangle orbits relevant for wires. As a result, in cluster supershell structures there are more oscillations (about 10) between two beats. For nanowires, there are approximately only two oscillations between two successive beats and the positions of beats have less resolution. This fact makes also the observation of beat shifts harder for wires than for clusters. Moreover,

the magnitudes of the shifts are smaller for wires than for clusters. For example, the beat shift from Na to Al densities is about $0.1\lambda_F$ for wires, whereas it is $0.4\lambda_F$ for clusters [26, 25]. This is due to several factors: First the potential softness itself and its effect on the electronic quantum spectrum may be different. Second, the orbital frequencies (≈ 5.2 and 5.7) for clusters make the factors of the last terms in equation (6) more than three times larger than those for wires. In the case of Na and Cs we estimate, using equation (6), that the beat shift for wires cannot be observed.

The effect of the potential softness to the beat shifts can be studied by changing the stabilized jellium model to the simple jellium model. (Actually, the cluster results quoted above have been obtained with the simple jellium model, and therefore their comparison with our stabilized jellium results is slightly inaccurate.) The stabilized jellium model corrects the jellium potential by adding a positive constant inside the background charge region in the case of low-density metals ($r_s > 4.18$), whereas the correction is negative for high-density metals ($r_s < 4.18$). The correction is small for Cs ($\simeq 0.25$ eV) but relevant ($\simeq -2.5$ eV) for Al. Therefore, the simple jellium model provides softer effective potentials for high-density wires and more abrupt potentials for low densities, increasing *a priori* the supershell beat shift with respect to the stabilized jellium model. According to our calculations for Al wires, the beat shift between the stabilized jellium and simple jellium results is $0.1\lambda_F$. In the simple jellium model the supershell beat shift from Na to Al is then twice as large as that in the stabilized jellium model. A difference of this order should be observable.

4. Conclusion

We have studied the stability of metallic nanowires modelling them as infinite jellium cylinders. The quantum-mechanical electronic structure has been solved self-consistently for systems corresponding to Al, Na and Cs metals. Thus, the whole range of metallic valence electron densities has been scanned through.

The shell and supershell structures of the energy oscillations have been analysed in the framework of the semiclassical theory, and its link with the quantum results has been pointed out. This has allowed us to determine the effect of the valence electron density in nanowires on the semiclassical orbits via the potential softness. We have found that the beat shifts between the supershell structures are mainly due to a phase change of the pendulum orbit.

It has been found that a low density of states at the Fermi level ($\text{DOS}(\epsilon_F)$) is directly related to stable wires. The relation between stability and $\text{DOS}(\epsilon_F)$ has a large importance in the effort to find stable magnetic solutions for metallic wires, because the magnetic solutions [3, 4] should appear in the regions of high $\text{DOS}(\epsilon_F)$.

A comparison with clusters, in which the supershell structure has been intensively studied, has been performed. Several reasons for the differences between the supershell structures of clusters and nanowires have been pointed out.

Recently, in the mechanically controllable break-junction experiments with alkali

metals [30], it has been found that the electronic shell behaviour dominates up to a particular radius, after which a transition to the atomic shell behaviour occurs. Therefore the range of applicability of the cylindrical jellium model is limited by this transition radius. It depends on the temperature and melting point of the metal, for example, for K at 100 K is about $2.2 \lambda_F$ [30]. This notion opens new lines of investigation, both theoretically as well as experimentally, in order to clarify the relative importance of electronic and atomic aspects in determining the shell structures.

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Figure captions

Figure 1. Oscillations in energy per unit length for Cs, Na and Al nanowires. The dashed stripes denote the supershell beat positions. The arrows pointing downwards give the positions of the conductance peaks and the dashed lines the beat positions in the experimental conductance histograms of Na nanowires[8].

Figure 2. Fourier transforms of the energy oscillations and the semiclassical orbits corresponding to each peak.

Figure 3. Radii (horizontal axis) at which the bottoms of different subbands of Na (upper panel) and Al wires (lower panel) touch the Fermi level. The m quantum number increases along the y-axis, and the points on each ascending diagonal have the same n quantum number. The states belonging to the same pendulum and triangular orbits have been connected with continuous and dashed lines, respectively. Straight vertical lines denote the positions of the clear energy maxima.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3